

Planting density, varieties effect on Growth of Green and Red lettuce under open condition (*Lactuca sativa* L.)

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Introduction

Lettuce (*Lactuca sativa* L.), an annual leafy vegetable of the Compositae family, is a widely cultivated, short-duration crop originating from the Mediterranean to Siberia. With a chromosomal count of $2n = 18$, it is among the most consumed and economically important vegetables globally (Coelho *et al.*, 2005). It is

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Abstract

A field experiment entitled “Effect of Planting Density on Growth and Quality of Green and Red Leaf Lettuce (*Lactuca sativa* L.)” was conducted during 2024–25 at the Department of Horticulture, V.N.M.K.V., Parbhani. The study aimed to determine the optimum planting density and suitable variety for enhanced growth and quality of lettuce under field conditions. The treatment combination were the four planting density viz., S₁: 30 cm × 30 cm, S₂: 45 cm × 15 cm, S₃: 45 cm × 30 cm and S₄: 45 cm × 45 cm with two varieties viz., Green leaf lettuce (V₁) and Red leaf lettuce (V₂). In case of planting density maximum number of leaves /plant (15.20, 17.35 and 22.55), leaf length (11.64 cm, 15.99 cm and 22.55 cm), leaf breadth (9.93 cm, 15.55 cm and 24.09), leaf area (24.11 cm², 91.38 cm² and 138.15 cm²) was recorded from S₄ whereas maximum plant height (13.69 cm, 18.68 cm and 24.58 cm) was recorded from S₁. In varieties maximum number of leaves/ plant (14.22, 16.38, 22.40), leaf breadth (9.43 cm, 13.82 cm and 22.77 cm) and leaf area (23.42 cm², 88.78 cm² and 132.85 cm²) recorded from green leaf lettuce. Whereas, maximum plant height (13.46 cm, 18.56 cm and 24.59 cm) and leaf length (10.92 cm, 14.24 cm and 21.63 cm) noted from red leaf lettuce.

Keywords : Growth, lettuce, planting density, quality, variety.

valued for its mild, crispy texture, slightly bitter taste, and milky sap when fresh. Commonly consumed in salads, it is often paired with vegetables like tomato and cucumber or served with dressings (Jangu *et al.*, 2022). Green and red leaf lettuce are widely consumed varieties known for their nutritional value and culinary versatility. Green leaf lettuce offers a mild,

slightly sweet flavour and crunchy texture, and is rich in vitamins A, C, and K, along with minerals such as potassium, calcium, and iron. Per 100 g edible portion (Gopalan and Balaraman, 1966). It also contains folate, carotenoids, phenolics, and antioxidants (Camejo et al., 2020). In contrast, red leaf lettuce has a slightly bitter taste and deep red pigmentation due to anthocyanins, contributing to its higher antioxidant content and commercial value (Gazula et al., 2007). Both types are low in calories, aid digestion, and are commonly used in salads, wraps, and soups. Proper plant spacing is crucial for maximizing vegetative growth and quality improvement in lettuce. Inappropriate spacing can lead to overcrowding or underutilization, reducing productivity. Optimal planting density promotes uniform growth by ensuring efficient use of moisture, nutrients, and light (Firoz et al., 2009). It also enhances yield, quality, and ease of intercultural operations, with potential yield increases of up to 25% in leafy vegetables (Bansal et al., 1995).

Materials and Methods

A field experiment was carried out during October 2024 to February 2025, to assess the combined effect of planting density and variety on growth and quality parameter in lettuce at Instructional-Cum Research Farm, Department of Horticulture, College of Agriculture, Vasant Rao Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth, Parbhani, India which is located at situated at 408.50 meter altitude above mean sea level and falls on 19°16' N latitude and 76°47' E longitude and has a sub-tropical climate. The soil of the experimental field was well drained and medium black with the soil pH 6.5, available N (175.65 kg/ha) available P (10.25 kg/ha), EC (0.5 ds/m), available K (314.05 kg/ha). The experiment was laid out in Factorial Randomized Block Design comprising of 8 treatments which are replicated thrice. Treatment combination consisted of two factors, one with four different planting density *i.e.*, S₁: 30 cm ×

30 cm, S₂: 45 cm × 15 cm, S₃: 45 cm × 30 cm and S₄: 45 cm × 45 cm and other with two different varieties *i.e.*, green leaf lettuce and red leaf lettuce. There were 8 treatment combinations such as V₁S₁, V₁S₂, V₁S₃, V₁S₄, V₂S₁, V₂S₂, V₂S₃ and V₂S₄. There were 24 plots and the size of the plot was 2 m x 1.5 m. The data obtained for different parameters were statistically analyzed to find out the significance difference of different planting density and variety.

Results and Discussion

Growth parameters

Plant height (cm)

Statistically significant variation on plant height of lettuce was shown due to different planting densities at 20, 40DAT and at harvest (Table 1). At different days after transplanting (DAT) the tallest plant (13.69, 18.68 and 24.58 cm) at 20, 40DAT and at harvest respectively was recorded from S₁ (30 cm × 30 cm). On the other hand, the shortest plant (10.25, 14.49 and 20.12 cm) at 20, 40DAT and at harvest respectively was found from S₄ (45 cm × 45 cm). Closer spacing intensified competition for nutrients, water, and light, which restricted lateral growth and promoted vertical elongation, resulting in increased plant height. Alahi et al. (2014) reported similar findings from the closest spacing in lettuce. Among varieties V₂ (Red leaf lettuce) have found highest plant height (13.46, 18.56 and 24.59 cm) as compare to V₁ (Green leaf lettuce) recorded minimum height (10.12, 14.06 and 19.59 cm) at 20, 40DAT and at harvest respectively. The interaction effect of planting density and variety on lettuce plant height was nonsignificant at 20 DAT but significant at 40 DAT and harvest. At 40 DAT, the tallest plants (21.9 cm) were observed in V₂S₁ (Red leaf lettuce + 30×30 cm), while the shortest (13.0 cm) was in V₁S₄ (Green leaf lettuce + 45×45 cm). Similar trends were noted at harvest, with maximum height (28.1 cm) in V₂S₁ and minimum (18.0 cm) in V₁S₄.

Table 1: Effect of different planting density ,varieties and their interaction on plant height (cm) and number of leaves per plant.

Treatment	Plant height (cm)			Number of leaves per plant		
	20DAT	40DAT	At harvest	20DAT	40DAT	At harvest
Variety						
V ₁ (Green lettuce)	10.12	14.06	19.59	14.22	16.38	22.40
V ₂ (Red lettuce)	13.46	18.56	24.59	13.24	15.75	19.26
SE (m)±	0.26	0.2334	0.2654	0.25	0.16	0.26
CD at 5 %	0.79	0.708	0.805	0.75	0.48	0.78
Planting density						
S ₁ (30×30cm)	13.69	18.68	24.58	12.32	14.58	19.00
S ₂ (45×15cm)	12.26	16.38	22.55	13.08	15.69	20.00
S ₃ (45×30cm)	10.97	15.69	21.13	14.30	16.65	21.78
S ₄ (45×45cm)	10.25	14.49	20.12	15.20	17.35	22.55
SE (m)±	0.37	0.33	0.38	0.35	0.22	0.36
CD at 5 %	1.12	1.00	1.14	1.06	0.68	1.10
Interaction (V×S)						
V1S1	11.1	15.4	21.0	12.53	14.70	20.00
V1S2	10.8	14.2	20.2	13.27	15.50	21.00
V1S3	9.4	13.7	19.2	15.02	17.30	24.02
V1S4	9.2	13.0	18.0	16.06	18.07	24.60
V2S1	16.3	21.9	28.1	12.10	14.50	18.00
V2S2	13.7	18.6	24.9	12.90	15.88	19.00
V2S3	12.5	17.7	23.1	13.59	16.00	19.55
V2S4	11.3	16.0	22.2	14.35	16.63	20.50
SE (m)±	0.52	0.47	0.53	0.49	0.32	0.51
CD at 5 %	1.59	1.42	1.61	1.49	0.96	1.55

Table 2: Effect of different planting density ,varieties and their interaction on leaf length (cm), leaf breadth (cm) and leaf area (cm²) .

Treatment	Leaf length (cm)			Leaf breadth (cm)			Leaf area (cm ²)		
	20 DAT	40 DAT	At harvest	20 DAT	40 DAT	At harvest	20 DAT	40 DAT	At harvest
Variety									
V ₁ (Green lettuce)	9.99	13.19	19.96	9.43	13.82	22.77	23.42	88.78	132.85
V ₂ (Red lettuce)	10.92	14.24	21.63	9.10	12.53	21.49	21.64	86.49	130.68
SE (m)±	0.28	0.16	0.19	0.07	0.17	0.15	0.11	0.17	0.24
CD at 5 %	0.85	0.50	0.56	0.23	0.51	0.47	0.35	0.52	0.73
Planting density									
S ₁ (30×30cm)	9.45	11.65	18.80	8.83	11.48	18.43	20.97	83.99	124.87
S ₂ (45×15cm)	10.13	12.88	20.43	9.05	11.80	22.52	22.00	86.47	127.81
S ₃ (45×30cm)	10.62	14.36	21.40	9.27	13.88	23.49	23.04	88.69	136.23
S ₄ (45×45cm)	11.64	15.99	22.55	9.93	15.55	24.09	24.11	91.38	138.15
SE (m)±	0.40	0.23	0.26	0.10	0.24	0.22	0.16	0.24	0.34
CD at 5 %	1.20	0.71	0.80	0.32	0.73	0.66	0.49	0.73	1.04
Interaction (V×S)									
V1S1	9.74	11.43	18.45	8.87	11.93	18.48	21.63	85.01	125.10
V1S2	9.88	12.77	19.35	9.05	12.06	23.42	22.63	88.04	129.61
V1S3	10.01	13.60	20.02	9.47	15.17	24.43	24.29	90.10	137.58
V1S4	10.33	14.98	22.04	10.3 5	16.13	24.76	25.12	91.96	139.10
V2S1	9.15	11.87	19.16	8.79	11.03	18.37	20.30	82.98	124.64
V2S2	10.37	13.00	21.50	9.05	11.53	21.62	21.37	84.89	126.00

V2S3	11.22	15.11	22.79	9.07	12.60	22.55	21.79	87.28	134.87
V2S4	12.94	16.99	23.06	9.51	14.97	23.42	23.09	90.79	137.20
SE (m)±	0.56	0.33	0.37	0.15	0.34	0.31	0.23	0.34	0.48
CD at 5 %	1.70	1.00	1.13	0.45	1.03	0.93	0.70	1.03	1.46

Number of leaves per plant :

Analysis of the result showed that different planting densities significantly affected the number of leaves per plant of lettuce. Statistically significant variation was recorded for number of leaves per plant of lettuce (Table 1). At different days after transplanting the maximum number of leaves per plant (15.20, 17.35 and 22.55) at 20, 40DAT and at harvest respectively was obtained from S₄ (45 cm × 45 cm). At the same condition, the minimum number of leaves/plant (12.32, 14.58 and 19.00) at 20, 40DAT and at harvest respectively was recorded from S₁ (30 cm × 30 cm). Increase in planting density lead to higher number of leaves per plant, likely due to space availability for upward and outward. Similar results were reported by Hasan et al. (2017), Akter (2020) and Ajay (2023) in lettuce. Among the varieties variety V₁ (Green leaf lettuce) produced maximum number of leaves per plant at 20, 40DAT and at harvest (14.22, 16.34 and 22.40) respectively which was significantly superior over variety V₂ (Red leaf lettuce) which recorded (13.24, 15.80 and 19.26) number of leaves respectively. Garg (2020) and Kumar (2022) also reported similar findings. The combined influence of planting density and variety showed a nonsignificant effect on the number of leaves at 20 DAT but was significant at 40 DAT and harvest. At 40 DAT, the highest leaf count (18.07) was observed in V₁S₄ (Green leaf lettuce + 45×45 cm), while the lowest (14.50) was recorded in V₂S₁ (Red leaf lettuce + 30×30 cm). Similarly, at harvest, V₁S₄ (Green leaf lettuce + 45 cm × 45 cm) recorded the maximum number of leaves (24.60), whereas the minimum (18.00) was noted in V₂S₁ (Red leaf lettuce + 30 cm × 30 cm).

Leaf length (cm) :

Leaf length was significantly influenced due to different planting density at 20, 40DAT and at

harvest respectively (Table 2). The highest leaf length (11.64, 15.99 and 22.55 cm) was observed from S₄ (45 cm × 45 cm) and the lowest leaf length (9.45, 11.65 and 18.80 cm) was recorded from S₁ (30 cm × 30 cm). It was revealed that with the increases of planting density leaf length showed increasing trend. In case of closer planting density plant compete for light and with the time being leaf length decreases. Similar results have been reported by Jangu (2022) in lettuce. The maximum length of leaves (10.92, 14.24 and 21.63 cm) was recorded in V₂ (Red leaf lettuce) and minimum leaf length (9.99, 13.19 and 19.96 cm) was found in V₁ (Green leaf lettuce) at 20, 40DAT and at harvest respectively. Wide variation for this character was also reported by Garg (2020) in lettuce. Analysis of the interaction between planting density and variety revealed nonsignificant effect on the leaf length at 20 DAT but was significant at 40 DAT and harvest. At 40 DAT, maximum leaf length (16.99 cm) were recorded with the treatment combinations V₂S₄ (Red leaf lettuce + 45 cm × 45 cm). Whereas minimum leaf length (11.43 cm) was recorded under treatment combination V₁S₁ (Green leaf lettuce + 30 cm × 30 cm). At harvest maximum leaf length at harvest (23.06 cm) were recorded with the treatment combinations V₂S₄ (Red leaf lettuce + 45 cm × 45 cm) Whereas, minimum leaf length (18.45 cm) was recorded under treatment combination V₁S₁ (Green leaf lettuce + 30 cm × 30 cm).

Leaf breadth(cm) :

Leaf breadth of lettuce was significantly influenced due to different planting densities. The highest leaf breadth (9.93, 15.55 and 20.29 cm) at 20, 40DAT and at harvest respectively was observed from S₄ (45 cm × 45 cm) and lowest leaf breadth (8.83, 11.48 and 18.43 cm) was observed from S₁ (30 cm × 30 cm). This indicates that leaf breadth increased

with increasing plant planting density, likely due to Reduced competition for resources such as light, nutrients, and space. Similar results have been reported by Jangu (2022) in lettuce. Among the varieties the maximum leaf breadth (9.43, 13.82 and 22.77 cm) was recorded in V₁ (Green leaf lettuce) and minimum leaf breadth (9.10, 12.53 and 21.49 cm) was found in V₂ (Red leaf lettuce) at 20, 40DAT and at harvest respectively. Evaluating the effect of planting density and variety together showed nonsignificant effect on the leaf length at 20 DAT but was significant at 40 DAT and harvest. At 40 DAT, maximum leaf breadth per plant at 40 DAT (16.13 cm) were recorded with the treatment combinations V₁S₄ (Green leaf lettuce + 45 cm × 45 cm). Whereas, minimum leaf breadth (11.03 cm) was recorded under treatment combination V₂S₁ (Red leaf lettuce + 30 cm × 30 cm). At harvest maximum leaf breadth per plant at harvest (24.76 cm) were recorded with the treatment combinations V₁S₄ (Green leaf lettuce + 45 cm × 45 cm). Whereas, minimum leaf breadth (18.37 cm) were recorded under treatment combination V₂S₁ (Red leaf lettuce + 30 cm × 30 cm).

Leaf area (cm²) :

For plant density, the topmost leaf area (24.11, 91.38, 138.15 cm²) was noted from wider planting density S₄ (45 cm × 45 cm) whereas, the smallest leaf area (20.97, 83.99, 124.87 cm²) was seen in closet planting density S₁ (30 cm × 30 cm) at 20, 40DAT and at harvest respectively. Wider spacing promoted larger leaf development by reducing competition for light and allowing better canopy expansion. Similar findings were reported by Yordanova and Nikolov (2017) and Akter et al. (2020) in lettuce. The maximum leaf area (23.42, 88.78 and 132.85 cm²) reported in V₁ (Green leaf lettuce) and minimum leaf area (21.64, 86.49 and 130.68 cm²) was found in V₂ (Red leaf lettuce) at 20, 40DAT and at harvest respectively. Similar findings were reported by Garg (2020) in lettuce. Evaluating the effect of planting density and variety together showed nonsignificant effect on the leaf length at 20 DAT but was significant at 40 DAT and harvest.

At 40 DAT, maximum leaf area at 40 DAT (90.96 cm²) were recorded with the treatment combinations V₁S₄ (Green leaf lettuce + 45 cm × 45 cm). Whereas, minimum leaf area (82.98 cm²) was recorded under treatment combination V₂S₁ (Red leaf lettuce + 30 cm × 30 cm). At harvest Maximum leaf area at harvest (139.10 cm²) were recorded with the treatment combinations V₁S₄ (Green leaf lettuce + 45 cm × 45 cm). Whereas, minimum leaf length (124.64 cm²) was recorded under treatment combination V₂S₁ (Red leaf lettuce + 30 cm × 30 cm).

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